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Research Article

**EFFICACY OF TERMINAL DEOXYNUCLEOTIDYL
TRANSFERASE (TDT) AS A DIAGNOSTIC MARKER IN
ACUTE LYMPHOBLASTIC LEUKEMIA****¹Dr Nouman Shafique, ²Dr Muhammad Tehseen Ali, ³Dr Farhan Ghaffar Bhatti
^{1,2,3}Nishtar Medical University, Multan.****Article Received:** March 2020**Accepted:** April 2020**Published:** May 2020**Abstract:**

Aim: To differentiate Acute Lymphoblastic Leukemia from Acute Myeloid Leukemia and to Isolate Terminal deoxynucleotidyl transferase positive blasts in CSF.

Place and Duration: In the Oncology department of Mayo Hospital Lahore for one year duration from March 2019 to March 2020.

Methods: The study covered 35 persons. They were divided into three groups. They were elected from the Mayo Hospital, Lahore. 35 cases were divided into three groups: - Group A included 25 patients with acute lymphoblastic leukemia. Patients from group B 05 with acute myeloid leukemia and patients with a normal control group from group C 05 subjects.

Results: Patients with Acute lymphoblastic leukaemia (Group A) had Terminal deoxynucleotidyl transferase positive blasts in peripheral blood smear while acute myeloid leukaemia (Group B) had no Tdt+ve Blasts in peripheral blood smear. Out of 25 patients of ALL, 06 (24%) patients of ALL had Tdt positive blasts in Cerebrospinal Fluid Staining.

Keywords: Terminal deoxynucleotidyl transferase (TDT), ALL, AML.

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INTRODUCTION:

Leukemia is a group of diseases in which the abnormal proliferation of hematopoietic cells causes progressive infiltration of the bone marrow, but in some respects this is especially true for lymphatic tissues. As a disease affecting the bone marrow, leukemia was first described by Neumann in 1870. Leukemia blast cells accumulate in the bone marrow and suppress the differentiation and proliferation of normal hematopoietic cells. Acute leukemia is > 50% lymphoblast or myeloblast in the bone marrow. It is caused by a lymphopoietic stem cell (acute lymphocytic leukemia, ALL) or a hemopoietic stem cell or progenitor cell (acute myeloid leukemia, AML). Chronic leukemia includes two main types: chronic myelogenous leukemia (CML) and chronic lymphocytic leukemia (CLL). Other chronic types include hairy cell leukemia, pro-lymphocytic leukemia, and various leukemia / lymphoma syndromes.

METHODOLOGY:

This study was held in the Oncology department of Mayo Hospital Lahore for one year duration from March 2019 to March 2020. The study covered 35 people. They were divided into three groups. Thirty-five people were divided into the following groups:

Group A: Included 25 patients of acute lymphoblastic leukemia.

Group B: Included 05 patients of acute myeloid leukemia.

Group C: Included 05 normal control subjects.

Specimen collection: A minimum of 5 ml. blood was drawn from each patient with a sterile disposable syringe fitted with 21 gauge needle and immediately transferred to a clean glass tube containing EDTA in ratio of 1 mg of EDTA per ml of blood for routine haematological investigations. Push smears for routine and special stains were immediately prepared from blood without adding EDTA to it, smears for TdT staining were air dried followed by fixation in methyl alcohol and subsequently wrapped in aluminium foil and stored desiccated at -20° C.

RESULTS:

The details of results are given in tables 1, 2 and 3

Table 1: Comparison of blasts in group A and B

Groups	Group A (ALL)	Group B (AML)
Mean ± SD	32.2 ± 4.21	56.0 ± 5.92
Range	09 – 85	32 – 78
Total	25	05

Statistical Analysis A vs B p<0.05 (Significant)

Table 2: Comparison of Terminal deoxynucleotidyl transferase +VE blasts in peripheral blood smear in group A and B

Groups	Group A (ALL)	Group B (AML)
Mean ± SD	53.0 ± 11.63	Zero
Range	29 – 72	Zero
Total	25	Zero

Statistical Analysis A vs B p<0.01 (Highly Significant)

Table 3: Comparison of TdT +ve blasts in CSF in group A and B

Groups	+ve patients	-ve patients	Total
Group A	06 (24%)	19 (76%)	25
Group B	Zero	05 (100%)	05

Statistical Analysis A vs B p<0.01 (Highly Significant)

DISCUSSION:

In this study, the mean SD values of blasts in Groups A, B and C were 32.2 ± 4.21 and 56.0 ± 5.92, respectively, with ranges of 09-85 and 32-78%. Group B showed an increase in the number of blasts compared to group A, and the difference was

statistically significant (p <0.01). This study confirms the results of Firkin *et al.* (1989), Bradstock *et al.* (1980) and Bradstock *et al.* (1995), who also observed these changes in patients with ALL and AML. In this study, TdT Positive Blasts in CSF of Group A were 24% (06) while group B (AML) did not show any TdT

+ve blast in CSF and different was highly significant ($p < 0.01$) statistically. These results are consistent with the study of Bradstock et al (1980)6, Casper et al (1983)8, Firkin et al (1989)5, who also observed Tdt+ve blasts in CSF of ALL patients (Group A). Patients of AML (Group B) showed no Tdt+ve blasts in CSF.

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